

Research Productivity of India's scientific literature on Library Science and Information Science

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Abstract

The study provides a comprehensive analysis of trends of the India's scientific research on Library Science and Information Science from the first published literature up to March, 2022. Relevant documents were searched using in search field of Address 'India' and in Web of Science Categories we refined by "Library Science Information Science", to retrieve relevant literature using the Web of Science (WOS) database. Scientometric indicators were analysed using HistCite and VOSviewer. A total of 1851 publications with an h-index of 63 were retrieved from the database. Overall, articles retrieved were written by 2912 authors, published in 99 journals, 80 countries represented, and 12.42 average citations per document. Indian Institute of Management led the list of contributing institutions with 89 articles. The National Institute of Science and Technology & Development Studies, the A.P.J Abdul Kalam Technology University and Satija MP was the top funding agencies that enhanced research on Library Science and Information Science and supported more than 120 articles. USA collaborates the most significant proportion 187 (10.1 %) India on Library Science Information Science publication closely followed by United Kingdom in the number of publications 95 (5.2 %). The study provides insight into the India's research perspective for the scientific progress on the Library Science Information Science thus significantly impacting and supporting intervention towards improving Information Scientist occurrence.

1. Introduction

1.1. Information Science

Information science includes any professional who works with, researches about, or learns about the management of information in any form. Whether you are interested in storing, retrieving, describing, organizing, representing, or providing information to others.

1.2. Library Science

The study of library science and the concepts and practices of library operation and administration. Since antiquity, libraries have existed, but library science emerged as a distinct area of study only in the second half of the nineteenth century. It was increasingly subsumed within the broader discipline of information science with the knowledge explosion of the twentieth century.

1.3. Scientometrics

The emergence of metric sciences such as librmetrics, bibliometrics, scientometrics, cybermetrics or webometrics, and finally informatics can be attributed to the twentieth century¹. The goal is to examine the knowledge domain using quantitative methodologies and approaches. Because of the necessity to quantify and analyze the massive investments in science and technology (S&T) sectors, particularly in research and development activities², scientometrics is becoming increasingly popular. Journals are the major means of disseminating research and intellectual material, and publishing papers in high-impact, high-quality national and international journals is closely linked to obtaining respect, reputation, and academic performance in the higher education setting.

2. Methodology

2.1. Study design

The study adopted the scientometric method to analyze quantitatively and qualitatively documents indexed in the Web of Science (WoS) database. The study period of the current research was limited from the year 1989 to March, 2022.

2.2. Search strategy

The WoS database was comprehensively searched in the Science Citation Index Expanded (SCIE) and Social Science Citation Index (SSCI) databases of the Web of Science Core Collection by search scenarios in the search field Address search string “India” and then its refined by “Information Science Library Science”. Only articles published in all languages were retrieved. A total of 1851 documents were extracted from WoS. Bibliometric indicators include the year of publications, authors, region, subject areas, countries, institutions, journals, and funding agencies enhancing library and information science, country collaboration. Authorship productivity was presented in the final analysis.

2.3. Data analysis

The metadata of the effect of Information Science Library Science was exported from WoS and save in Plain.tXt format for final analysis. HistCite software was used to analyze and visualize direct citation linkages between scientific papers and VOSviewer.Var1.6.6 was used to developed scientometric maps between documents to examine their characteristics.

3. Results

3.1. The Basic Characteristics of India’s Publications on Information Science Library Science

The data search result included 1851 articles, cumulatively had 18,699 citations, h-Index 63, and average citations of 12.42 per document.

3.2. Highly Cited Article

The ten top-cited articles on the effects of the India’s publications on Information Science and Library Science captured as “highly cited papers” were in Library and Information

Science academic field based on a highly cited threshold and publication year. The top-cited articles were mainly in the field of Information Science Library Science. The highest number of citations attained was 428 for the article titled “Too Big to Fail: Large Samples and the p-Value Problem,” published in Information Systems Research. The second top-cited was published in the Information Society for the “Research approaches to mobile use in the developing world: A review of the literature” with a total citation of 336. The article “What motivates customers to participate in social commerce? The impact of technological environments and virtual customer experiences” published by the Information and Management amassed 316 citations in the Web of Science. The top ten cited articles’ citations range from 200 to 428.

S.No	Articles	Citations
1	849 Lin MF, Lucas HC, Shmueli G Too Big to Fail: Large Samples and the p-Value Problem INFORMATION SYSTEMS RESEARCH. 2013 DEC; 24 (4): 906-917	428
2	567 Donner J Research approaches to mobile use in the developing world: A review of the literature INFORMATION SOCIETY. 2008; 24 (3): 140-159	336
3	940 Zhang H, Lu YB, Gupta S, Zhao L What motivates customers to participate in social commerce? The impact of technological environments and virtual customer experiences INFORMATION & MANAGEMENT. 2014 DEC; 51 (8): 1017-1030	316
4	955 Gangwar H, Date H, Ramaswamy R Understanding determinants of cloud computing adoption using an integrated TAM-TOE model JOURNAL OF ENTERPRISE INFORMATION MANAGEMENT. 2015; 28 (1): 107-130	267
5	409 Gupta MP, Jana D E-government evaluation: A framework and case study GOVERNMENT INFORMATION QUARTERLY. 2003; 20 (4): 365-387	250

6	254 Mehtre BM, Kankanhalli MS, Lee WF Shape measures for content based image retrieval: A comparison INFORMATION PROCESSING & MANAGEMENT. 1997 MAY; 33 (3): 319-337	243
7	1640 Dwivedi YK, Hughes L, Ismagilova E, Aarts G, Coombs C, et al. Artificial Intelligence (AI): Multidisciplinary perspectives on emerging challenges, opportunities, and agenda for research, practice and policy INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF INFORMATION MANAGEMENT. 2021 APR; 57: Art. No. 101994	225
8	1262 Kamboj S, Sarmah B, Gupta S, Dwivedi Y Examining branding co-creation in brand communities on social media: Applying the paradigm of Stimulus-Organism-Response INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF INFORMATION MANAGEMENT. 2018 APR; 39: 169-185	206
9	588 Gupta B, Dasgupta S, Gupta A Adoption of ICT in a government organization in a developing country: An empirical study JOURNAL OF STRATEGIC INFORMATION SYSTEMS. 2008 JUN; 17 (2): 140-154	205
10	1060 Saif H, He YL, Fernandez M, Alani H Contextual semantics for sentiment analysis of Twitter INFORMATION PROCESSING & MANAGEMENT. 2016 JAN; 52 (1): 5-19	199

3.3. Most Active Journals

The 1851 eligible articles were published in 99 journals based on the search queries, of which 297 were identified published in the *Scientometrics*, followed by the *Electronic Library* by 111, *International Journal of Information Management* by 100, and *Journal of Enterprise Information Management* by 87 articles. The majority of the article was published in a specialized journal for research in Information Science. Approximately 900 articles were published in the top 10 listed journals, with 13,682 total citations. The number of articles published in the top 10 journals ranged from 40 to 297.

S.No	Journal	Publications	Citations
1	SCIENTOMETRICS	297	3795
2	ELECTRONIC LIBRARY	111	868
3	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF INFORMATION MANAGEMENT	100	3822
4	JOURNAL OF ENTERPRISE INFORMATION MANAGEMENT	87	1173
5	INFORMATION PROCESSING & MANAGEMENT	82	1781
6	KNOWLEDGE ORGANIZATION	71	109
7	JOURNAL OF KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT	66	1215
8	JOURNAL OF GLOBAL INFORMATION MANAGEMENT	63	238
9	PROGRAM-ELECTRONIC LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SYSTEMS	53	434
10	JOURNAL OF INFORMATION SCIENCE	42	247

3.4. Active Authors

A total of 2912 authors contributed to Information Science Library Science research. The topmost active authors based on the authors total citations, and the number of publications. Satija M P had 66 articles with 46 citations, followed by Prathap G with 57 articles with 470 Citations; Kumar S with 43 articles received 561 citations among others.

S.No	Author	Publications	Citations
1	Satija MP	66	46
2	Prathap G	57	470
3	Kumar S	43	561
4	Gupta S	36	1125
5	Gupta BM	35	418
6	Garg KC	26	494
7	Kumar V	25	292
8	Kumar A	23	273
9	Gul S	22	114
10	Dwivedi YK	20	1180

3.5. Most active and collaborative countries (80)

About 80 countries collaborative to Information Science Library Science publications. The USA was the most productive country published 187 articles and received 3862 citations, followed by UK published 95 articles and received 2628 citations , China (Publications = 55; Citations = 797), and Australia (Publications = 42; Citations = 480) were in the top four influential countries. Meanwhile, the US was the most collaborative country based on the Publications and other collaborative countries are reported in the below table.

S.No.	Country	Publications	Citations
1	USA	187	3862
2	UK	95	2628
3	Peoples R China	55	797
4	Australia	42	480
5	France	40	822
6	Canada	22	482
7	Singapore	20	661
8	Malaysia	19	83
9	Netherlands	19	517
10	Saudi Arabia	18	305

3.6. Keyword Analysis

The frequency occurrence of Keywords is shown in India with frequency (250), followed by ‘Information’(200), ‘Research’ (184), ‘Indian’ (182), ‘Analysis’ (154), ‘Based’(151), “Using”,(136), ‘Based’ (151), ‘Knowledge’ (111),‘Social’ (109), and ‘Technology’ (108).

S.No	Words	Publications	Citations
1	INDIA	250	2366
2	INFORMATION	200	2125
3	RESEARCH	184	3442
4	INDIAN	182	1884
5	ANALYSIS	154	2474
6	BASED	151	1663
7	USING	136	1416
8	KNOWLEDGE	111	1556

9	SOCIAL	109	2075
10	TECHNOLOGY	108	1287

3.7. Year Wise Publications

India's research output on Information Science and Library Science was recorded and retrieved as a cumulative total of 1851 during study period 1989 to 2022. Highest publications in the year 2021 with 200 publications and received 1130 citations followed by 168 publications in the year of 2020 followed by 2018 with 113 publications. Highest citation in the year 2018 received 2323 citations for 113 publications.

S.No	Year	Publications	Citations	S.No	Year	Publications	Citations
1	1989	26	116	18	2006	39	602
2	1990	15	41	19	2007	34	335
3	1991	17	90	20	2008	46	1362
4	1992	20	332	21	2009	48	578
5	1993	23	139	22	2010	52	909
6	1994	18	75	23	2011	56	958
7	1995	25	182	24	2012	45	503
8	1996	14	39	25	2013	45	890
9	1997	16	366	26	2014	91	1267
10	1998	38	426	27	2015	82	1331
11	1999	25	255	28	2016	81	1169
12	2000	25	275	29	2017	102	1515
13	2001	22	274	30	2018	113	2323
14	2002	31	290	31	2019	101	1738
15	2003	27	568	32	2020	168	1938
16	2004	25	380	33	2021	200	1130
17	2005	33	480	34	2022	52	25

3.8. Most Productive Institutions and Funding Agencies (1640)

Indian Institute of Management was the top organization with 89 publications its obtained 1875 citations and the National Institute of Science Technology & Development

Studies had 80 publications received 1206 citations followed by Indian Institute of Technology with 70 publications among others in the top ten shown in below table.

S.No.	Institution	Publications	Citations
1	Indian Institute of Management	89	1875
2	National Institute of Science Technology & Development Studies	80	1206
3	Indian Institute Technology	70	1700
4	Indian Statistical Institute	54	327
5	Indian School Business	31	1012
6	University of Delhi	30	269
7	Swansea University	29	1656
8	University of Kashmir	29	181
9	Guru Nanak Dev University	26	123
10	Indian Institute of Technology Delhi	26	746

Conclusion

Information Science and Library Science have emerged as an essential subject for knowledge management and information sharing it can be used by researchers having different disciplines for various aspects. Information Science and Library Science represents the integration approach of different subject domains. The function of Information Science and Library Science includes data storing, displaying, data analysis, management and retrieval. The present study determine increasing trend towards Information and Library Science research among researchers. The average publication was 12.42% and highest publication has been registered in the year 2021 with 200 publications. The highest paper published from USA, then UK, China, Australia and others during the marked study period. Most productive author was Satija M P with 66 publications and Prathap G has contributed with 57 publications.

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3. <https://eprints.soton.ac.uk/264418/>

4. Laksham, S., Surulinathi, M., Balasubramani, R., & Srinivasaragavan, S. (2020). Mapping the research output on Coronavirus: A Scientometric Study.

5. Ying Chen, Xiaojun Zhang, Shixiang Chen, Yanwen Zhang, Yulu Wang, Qi Lu, Yue Zhao, Bibliometric analysis of mental health during the COVID-19 pandemic, *Asian Journal of Psychiatry*, Volume 65, 2021, 102846, ISSN 1876-2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajp.2021.102846>.

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